

ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE SECURITY USING SOCIAL STUDIES PEDAGOGICAL
APPROACH

ADEMOLA, O.I.
Department of Curriculum &
Instructions
Alvan-Ikoku Federal College Of
Education Owerri
Email: adexventures03@gmail.com
08033740179

By
EBEBE, I.E. PhD
Department Social Studies
Alvan-Ikoku Federal
College of Education
Owerri.
Drebebe19@gmail.com
07066769989

Uzoagba B. C. PhD
Department of Social Studies
Alvan Ikoku Federal College of
Education, Owerri
Phone: 080366368741,
Email:
uzoagbabc23@gmail.com

Being A Paper Presented at the Third International Conference of Social Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (SOSTAN) Held at Federal College of Education Technical, Omoku, Rivers State.

Date: 1ST -3RD of September, 2021

Abstract

Security is a virtue which every nation should embrace to actualize sustainable security in the society. The case of insecurity is one of the issues and challenges faced in Nigeria which unequivocally is taken to a very high advanced magnitude which people are expected to all sought of attack like high rate of kidnapping, terrorism, militancy, incessant and sophisticated robbery, ritual killings, bombing among other. This paper discussed some of the needed pedagogical approach needed as necessary shifts to position Social Studies education as a means of achieving sustainable security in Nigeria. Suggestions were made among others that the teaching of Social Studies should go in line towards achievement of Nigeria's national goals.

Keywords: Pedagogical Approach, Sustainable Security, and Social Studies

Introduction

The field of Social Studies education has found acceptance as area of study that could enhance human development towards sustainable security. This could be seen in the philosophy of Social Studies which is based on the quality and functionality of education in the society. This means that Social Studies has become the most profound bedrock through which learners can identify problems and find a lasting solution to such problems encountered in their environments. Social Studies scholars often respond to current happenings like insecurity, corruption, armed robbery, banditry, kidnapping yahoo-yahoo, yahoo plus are all traceable to social menace and thereby devising a means of achieving a balance between the desire of the people in the society and Social Studies objectives. One of the major outstanding pressing issues in Nigeria today is how to curb insecurity. Insecurity has to do with a situation whereby people are exposed to all sought of attacks like kidnapping high rate of killing, armed robbery, militancy, terrorism, bombing, Banditry, Unknown Gunmen, among others. This situation could be backed by Ofojegbe (2010) observation which stressed that insecurity has reached an unprecedented proportion in contemporary discourse on Nigeria's emerging democracy.

In recent times, the nation Nigeria is beclouded and plagued by social issues like insecurity, hostage taking, cold-blood killings, ethno-religion conflicts, among others in Nigeria. However, a situation like this always calls for questions like; what channel is suitable to address the prevalent situation towards sustainable security? Can proper teaching of Social Studies education be used as a means to salvage the ought scenario or can adoption of the proper techniques in teaching Social Studies helps to expose the learners to restore security in their environment? Based on the objectives of Social Studies which is designed to expose the learners to the do's and the don't's of the society. The discipline is considered necessary as a weapon to be adopted to check some of the menace of the society.

The Concept Security

Security simply means freedom from any form of danger or threat to a national ability to protect it cherished values and the well-being of its people. It could be termed national or human security (Iyaji & Igoche, 2019), while insecurity in contrary denotes the absence of peace, safety, the presence of danger, hazard that depicts a problematic condition. The adaption to crucial transformation changes socially, that are meant to promote the spirit of consciousness towards human security and project contemporary issues that would make learners functionally equipped

and exposed to some national and global issues of concern, such as insecurity and security consciousness in Nigeria, is meant to be achieved through an educational instrument called social studies curriculum. According to Mbakwem (2011) curriculum is the vehicle through which educational goals are realized.

Sustainable Security

Sustainability is defined as a way of living that meets the physical and environmental need of the current generation without depleting the resources available for future generation (Nolet, 2009). Philip-Ogoh (2008) states that security implies safety of the people from both violent and non-violent threat; he went further to stress that it is a condition that is characterized by freedom, safety for lives and even properties. Security is a sine quo non for survival of person or nation. However, sustainable security requires more than a reliance on air conventional powers to deflect threats, but also to maintain the moral authority to lead a global effort to overcome threats. To air common security, sustainable security demands that we should not only focus on the government but also with people, education sector, economic sector and all other sectors. Akinola (2012) pointed at the following as some of the strategies that can enhanced sustainable security.

- i. Eradication of extreme poverty and hunger
- ii. Achievement of universal primary education
- iii. Ensuring environmental suitability
- iv. Development of a global partnership for development
- v. Promotion of gender equality and empowerment of human

Sustainable security has to do with a bold rethinking of national security that introduces the nations of collection and human security and balancing of defense, diplomacy and development through educational sector. Sustainable security is relevant because looking at the situation of insecurity in Nigeria, the country is faced with a lot of social vices which to curb the situation needs a robust diplomatic and development capacities is needed through the educational sector to address collective threats and human insecurity through teaching some related topics like tolerance, obedience, etc through Social Studies education. however, sustainable security recognizes relationship between development of people through education. Insecurity and violent conflicts are enemies to growth and development because no developmental effort can succeed in an atmosphere of rancor and strife. For development to be sustained, resource management and usage must be in a manner that meet the needs of the present generation while preserving the environment

for the present and future generations. Every society by nature may adapt to some crucial transformations changes through the afore points mentioned points highlighted by Akinola which could be inform of social, economic, political and technological that are meant for civilized updating of man's values, security, attitudes, skills and knowledge for functional social living. In addition, it is also meant to promote the spirit of consciousness towards human security and to project contemporary issues that would make learners functionally equipped and exposed to some national and global issues of concern, such as curbing insecurity and security sustainability in Nigeria.

Concept of Social Studies

Social Studies has no singular outstanding accepted definition as far as the course deals with man in a changing environment. Thus, Social Studies has attracted a multitude of definitions. Based on the wave of re-awakening among Social Studies educators Nigeria towards repositioning Social Studies for sustainable future, many scholars define Social Studies thus; Hedgene (2009) defined Social Studies as a contemporary and environmentally formed field of study that provide the learners with requisite knowledge, skills values, attitudes and understanding of security. Nkire (2003) emphasized that Social Studies is a value laden subject which many other countries of the world have used to transform their societies. According to Danladi (2005) Social Studies education is field that studies man along with his activities in relation to his social, economic, political, cultural and physical environments for the purpose of acquiring skills, attitudes and values which are necessary for human (individual) and national (societal) development. Oyesikun (2019) also sees Social Studies as a curriculum instrument which embodies knowledge, positive attitudes, sound values and useful skills required and meant to be adequately acquired to help individual learners, live adapt, adjust, relate, interact, survive and to ensure the survival of others in order to contribute effectively to the growth, development and sustainability of the total environment for advancement of mankind, despite all the definitions of Social Studies, the outstanding fact that are common amongst scholars in the field remains that

- a. The main focus of the cause is on "Human (man) and man's relationship with the different environment.
- b. Identification of man's problems mostly current/contemporary issues, and exploring ways of findings a lasting solution.
- c. Exploring ways for equipping main with creative skills that can help in making man's abide a peaceful man's dwelling.

How successful has Social Studies objectives has been used in achieving national goals towards enhancing sustainable security. Every country like Nigeria has a goal or set of goals. A goal is a statement of vision- a statement that shows where an individual is going. There is a saying that if you do not know where you are going, any road can lead you there. Thus, Nigeria has a well-articulated goal as stated in National Policy of Education (2014), thus;

- i. A free and democratic society
- ii. A just and egalitarian society
- iii. A united strong and self-reliant nation
- iv. A great and dynamic economy
- v. A land of bright and full of opportunity for all citizens.

Since the main objectives of Social Studies at different levels of education in Nigeria is the production of responsible citizens, the assessment of the subject is the measure of the quality of responsible citizens the subjects have produced. Social studies curriculum entails all the concepts and generalization that are drawn from social sciences, arts, and humanities that concern man and the environment that are integrated as a discipline, planned and directed by the school. Social Studies represent fusion of several curriculum strands, including history, social sciences and that makes it an interdisciplinary subject. Social Studies Education is a discipline whose core drive is positioned around the study, analysis and understating of man and his environment. It focuses on developing a sympathetic appreciation of the diversity and inter-dependence of all members of the local community and the wider national and international amity and co-operation towards a healthy society. These have been proved to be possible only in an atmosphere of peace and tranquility. For Social Studies to achieve this role of promoting effective culture of peace in human societies, its theme should be hinged specifically on the general objectives and specific approach of teaching approach.

General Social Studies Objectives

The general objectives of social studies according Iwuamdi (2013) are:

1. To give man adequate information and knowledge about his society and the wider world.
2. To create in man awareness and appreciation of the benefits and results of scientific and technological discoveries and inventions and make him see how these affect his everyday life.

3. To develop intellect, skills, abilities and competencies and promote in him the spirit of enquiry, discovery, thinking and curiosity which will act as a spur to further investigation.
4. To make man what the society expects of its members so he will be able to judge his actions as well as those of others.
5. To familiarize individual with the norms of the society and thus socialize him in accordance with such norms. This-will enable him improve and perpetuate his society.
6. To help man become a good citizen and develop the necessary values and attitudes needed in a democracy.
7. To help man understand the differences that exist among individuals, environments, pursuits, capabilities and productions, and to make him realize that such differences as well as human rights should be appreciated and respected.
8. To create in man awareness and appreciations that community life in any human society is based on cooperation and interdependence at all levels right from the family to international level.
9. To expose man to the problems of his society and then lead him to develop appropriate functional approaches to the solution of such problems.
10. To help individual to develop proper value judgment and ability to criticize, analyze, select, and objectively evaluate issues and events in their proper perspectives.

There are reasons for social studies general objectives as a vehicle for sustainable security challenges in Nigeria, they are: Its introduction was induced by the wave of curriculum reform, adaptation and innovation that swept across Nigeria during the first decade of Nigerian independence. Basically, it is a response towards a goal-oriented curriculum, and reaction against the traditional system of education which has been viewed as being unsuitable for Nigeria. Traditional system of education is further accused of being teacher centered rather than being child-centered, laying great emphasis on subject and content-laden discipline; emphasizing memorization and ignoring individual learning styles by insisting on uniform patterns. Social Studies objectives were also adopted to help preserve the Nigerian image and cultural heritage in particular and Africa in general. This is aimed at ensuring that African cultural practices, traditions

and national heritage are preserved and passed on to future generations. It is also an avenue for new generation to be together beyond our differences

Concept of Pedagogical Approach

The pedagogical are commonly understood as the approaches to teaching. It is referred to the theory and practice of learning and how this process has an impact and its influence by the social, cultural, economic and the political factors or the students. This approach is constructive integrative, reflective inquiry-based learning and collaborative in nature. Bataineh (2015) asserted that prevalent methods like lecture and class discussion methods are the dominant methods used by teachers in teaching Social Studies. He therefore opined that the essence of evaluating this method is to fine-tune the cause as a subject that is very central to equip the learners with skills for national orientation and unity that can inculcate a long lasting national (security & creation towards self-reliance & sustainable security). Anyakoha (2008) observed that despite the factors that appear to adversely affect the teaching of values which can help in the knowledge of maintaining security, there seem to be ways of teaching methods that can promote the teaching of values. This study is focused on the application of the think–pair–share learning approach of social studies education in order to see its effectiveness in achieving sustainable security in Nigeria. To apply this approach in the field social studies, it is necessary to pay attention to the core phase guidelines as a characteristic of the think–pair–share approach. The following shows the steps for think–pair–share that must be of concern in learning activities (Tanujaya & Mumu, 2019; Tint & Nyunt, 2015).

- i. Think (Individual activity):** Each student is assigned to a problem given by the teacher. All students are given time to listen to their ideas and ideas before their love with the conditions are given. After that, the ideas and ideas are conveyed to the teacher before entering the next pairing stage.
- ii. Pair (Paired activities):** The teacher forms pairs and directs students to their ideas and ideas with their partners. Students will bring together ideas and ideas that have been designed previously. Each pair will reach the end at this stage before moving on to the next stage.
- iii. Share (Activities with all students):** Students share the results of their discussion in pairs with the whole class. In this phase, there will be a big discussion, where each pair will respond and comment to look for similarities or differences in views or opinions of various pairs.

This learning approach is part of active learning which provides opportunities for students to be involved in learning activities by thinking, in pairs and sharing with other students (Kusrini, 2012). Think Pair Share is a class-based active learning model, where students work on problems given by the teacher. Cahyani (2018) explained that the TPS approach can improve students' speaking skills not only in eloquent of words but also in sustaining peace in communities or societies they belong to. This really supports the emergence of self-confidence in students. Furthermore, the TPS learning approach is very useful for developing problem-solving skills for students in solving menace in community they belong to. Through discussion, students can employ critical thinking about how to curb insecurity in their communities / societies. This approach can also improve achievement, develop student interest in learning and self-esteem and increase collaboration between students. Another advantage obtained through the application of this approach is the process of learning activities to be interesting and fun for students, developing cognitive abilities and improving speaking skills (Sharma & Saarsar, 2018).

Achieving Sustainable Security using Social Studies Pedagogical Approach

Ikwumelu, Oyibe & Eluu (2019) substantiated that sustaining national security, depict the ability of the country to contend with changeable scenario or insecurities. Thus, Social Studies can help to build a nation's security through using the pedagogical approach 'Think – Pair- Share's concrete foundation of a learning culture, inundated with uncertainties which boost transformative and preventive commitment rather than lost of ability to combat insecurity. The use of the army and the police force that has been a strategy of fighting insecurity in Nigeria, has huge financial and human resource implications for the country and this does not portray Nigeria as a giant that she is suppose to be in Africa. The root of the problem is value orientation that can only be gotten through the quality teaching of Social Studies, to build a strong foundation that is preventive through the use of collaborative approach (Think- pair – share) and precautionary in nature rather than application of treatment (i.e. use of military). Oyibe & Nnamani (2016) are in congruence with the above when they stated that Social Studies contributes to the formation and building of human resources, the culture of constructing beliefs, attitudes, values and the ability for individuals and groups to collectively free themselves from ignorance to social control. Edinyang, Anyie & Gamba (2015) advocated for the use of Social Studies education to achieve inter-ethnic cooperation between Nigerians. Edinyang et al investigated the importance of Social Studies education in line with the philosophical goals and objectives of Social Studies in the Nigerian educational system through the promotion of value orientation, good citizenship education, peaceful cohabitation and tolerance for suitable inter-ethnic comprehension and promoting security.

In supporting the idea that social studies has the role of promoting peace education and security in Nigeria, Okobia (2001) maintained that; “the course content of Social Studies is geared at producing effective citizens and of foregoing a cohesive society that will support the motion of nation building by way of classroom mediation of social studies programme in our school and colleges. This can be done through aiding learners in understanding man as he relates to himself and stand by the truth. Social studies employs the use of concepts such as empathy, honesty, sympathy, tolerance, rationality, respect for persons needs and interest, decision making, interaction, independence, morality, co-operation, obedience, adaptation, loyalty, patriotism, authority, values, critical thinking, progress and rule of law under a democratic society. Looking at all this, it is quite clear that social studies has a role to play through its objectives of ensuring peace and security in Nigeria, but for efficiency and effectiveness in achieving peace and security, there is the need to enlarge the scope of Social Studies and its aims and objectives to accommodate the teaching of contemporary public issues, which peace and security are a significant part through the using of collaborative of good approach of pedagogical learning call Think- Pair-Share.

Social Studies Education is a discipline whose main thrust is centered around the study, analysis and understating of man and his environment. It focuses on developing a sympathetic appreciation of the diversity and inter-dependence of all members of the local community and the wider national and international comradeship and co-operation towards a healthy society. These have been proved to be possible only in an atmosphere of peace and tranquility. For Social Studies to achieve this role of promoting effective culture of peace in human societies, its theme should be hinged specifically on the culture of the people. (Aghulor and Iwegbu,2010).

In furtherance of the goals of Social Studies, Iyela and Audu (2006), noted that; the problem facing most African nations today is attributable to the influence of Western Civilization. Therefore, social studies as an interdisciplinary and problem solving subject can enhance the promotion of peace education by advocating “dialogue” in harmonizing relationship between nations, societies or groups globally. In supporting the idea that social studies has the role of promoting peace education and security in Nigeria, Okobia (2001) maintained that; “the course content of Social Studies is geared at producing effective citizens and of foregoing a cohesive society that will support the motion of nation building by way of classroom mediation of social studies programme in our school and colleges. This can be done through aiding learners in understanding man as he relates to himself and stand by the truth. Social studies employs the use of concepts such as empathy, honesty, sympathy, tolerance, rationality, respect for persons needs

and interest, decision making, interaction, independence, morality, co-operation, obedience, adaptation, loyalty, patriotism, authority, values, critical thinking, progress and rule of law under a democratic society. Looking at all this, it is quite clear that social studies has a role to play through its objectives of ensuring peace and security in Nigeria, but for efficiency and effectiveness in achieving peace and security, there is the need to enlarge the scope of Social Studies and its aims and objectives to accommodate the teaching of contemporary public issues, which peace and security are a significant part.

Conclusion

Aghulor, and Iwegbu. (2010) asserts that social studies can bring about peaceful environment for possible progress and general development if properly implemented at all school levels where social studies being taught in our schools. As earlier observed, social studies as a curriculum instrument have the capacity to inculcate security consciousness, culture and its imperatives. Hence, it should be vigorously taught in school from primary to senior secondary school to prepare young mind for effective citizenship so that they will be security compliant. Despite the anticipated acclaimed expectations from other field of studies; Social Studies in its own kind creates an enabling atmosphere for individuals to cope with the societal problems led to raising of questions on the extent of achievement of Social Studies objectives and how the insecurity in the society can of history. In response to this, social thinkers queried the effectiveness of Social Studies curriculum and they were of the opinion that the kind of skills, concepts, positive attitudes and critical thinking abilities needed to live in the modern society were to embrace think pair share technique approach.

Recommendations

Based on the above opinion thoughts of this study, the following recommendations were considered appropriate:

1. Social studies teachers should endeavour to make use of Think-Pair-Share instructional strategy in teaching and learning activities in all level of education instead of the continuous use of traditional (lecture) method. This is because Think-Pair-Share strategy promotes inter-dependency, cooperation, critical thinking, higher order thinking and problem-solving skills as well as social-inquiry research skills among students who have been exposed to them.

2. Collaboration is included as a key competence in several studies, however, extension of quality approach acquired in social studies should give high attention because it will give way for logic of expression for each learner in solving societal menace.
3. Strategic thinking also referred to as wise transformative social change and action competence captures the ability to set goals and plan, implement and evaluate what best ways of tackle insecurity.
4. A practical approach of using think pair share should also be encourage by our leaders by calling a town meeting to know the exert root cause of any insecurity.
5. Security should be given adequate attention because it has an automatic leakage effect on other spheres of national life.
6. Social studies incorporate all aspects of reforms and innovations needed to be acquired for the progress of the society.
7. Because this learning model is very useful, especially for teachers and students, it is hoped that this learning approach can be applied continuously in social studies and other subjects.
8. Another recommendation is the need for further research studies, especially on other factors that contribute to the successful application of think–pair–share in social studies learning.

References

- Akinola, D. B. (2012). Teacher evaluation of the contribution of Social Studies curriculum in achieving the millennium development goals in the North-central. An unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Abuja, Nigeria.
- Anyakoha, E. U. (2008). Home management for junior secondary schools. Onitsha: Africana Feb. Publishers Ltd.
- Aghulor, S.I. & Iwegbu C.J. (2010). "The place of social studies in peace education and security" in *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies XIII (1,2) 180-191*
- Bataineh, M. Z. (2015). Think-pair-share, co op-co op and traditional learning strategies on undergraduate academic performance. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 1/5, 217-226.
- Cahyani, F. (2018). The use of think pair share technique to improve students' speaking performance. *Research in English and Education (READ)*, 3(1), 76–90.
- Danladi E.N (2005). Social participation and values orientation of Nigerians for national integration: implication for social studies teachers a conference paper presented at the 20th SOSAN National Conference Wuse– Abuja.
- Edinyang, S. D. & Uba, I. (2015). Gender, socio-economic status, teacher qualification and their interaction on students' retention ability in Social Studies in Akwa-Ibom state, Nigeria. *International knowledge Sharing Plate form 2pp. 35 – 40.*
- Edinyang, S.D., Anyie, T.M. & Gamba, J. (2015). The role of Social Studies in the promotion of interethnic understanding among the people of Nigeria. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology Research*, 1(3): 1-7.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). National policy of education. Lagos: NERDC Press
- Iwuamadi F.N. (2013). Effective teaching of social studies. Owerri, clear image publishers.
- Iyaji, J.A. & Igoche, I. (2019). Enhancing security education in early childhood curriculum content for peace, national integration and sustainable development in Nigeria. *ICSHER JOURNAL*, 4(2), 64-69. Curbing Insecurity and Security Sustainability through Social Studies Curriculum Content Change and Implementation in Nigeria.
- Kusrini, E. (2012). Teaching speaking for senior high school school students using cooperative learning "think pair share". *Journal Aktif*, 18(3), 1–8.
- Makinde, M.A. (1979). Integrated social studies. a handbook of social studies for teachers. Oxford University Press.

- Mbakwem, J.N (2011). Determining new social studies teacher effectiveness in curriculum delivery. *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Studies*.18 (1), 135-142.
- Nolet, V. (2009). Preparing sustainability – literate teachers. *teacher college record*, 111, 409 – 442.
- Ofojegbe W.N. (2010). Community Policing and Peace Education: Panacea for combating criminal activities in Nigeria”. *Journal of Social Studies XIII (1,2)167-179*
- Oyesikun J. O.; Akinola D. B. & Umar B. B. (2019). Social studies as a tool for promoting security education towards sustainable development in Nigeria. *African scholars journal of contemporary education research (jcer-8) VOL. 15 NO. ISSN: 2359-1991*
- Oyibe, O. A., Nwafor, P.I. & Chukwu, C.O. (2019). Achieving sustainable national security through effective Social Studies pedagogy. *Journal of Educational Horizon*, 12(10): 111-119
- Oyibe, O.A. & Nnamani, S.C. (2016). Role of Social Studies in mobilizing Nigerians for global citizenship. *Journal of Research and Methods in Education*, 5(3): 52-58.
- Philip-Ogoh, A. (2008). The place of Social Studies enhancing national security in Nigeria. *NJSS Vol xi(1) Oct. 2008*.
- Tanujaya, B. & Mumu, J. (2019). Implementation of think-pair-share to mathematics instruction. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 13(4), 510–517. doi:10.11591/edulearn.v13i4.14353
- Tint, S. S. & Nyunt, E. E. (2015). Collaborative learning with think-pair-share technique. *Computer Applications: An International Journal*, 2(1), 1–11. doi:10.5121/caij.2015.2101
- Sharma, H. L. & Saarsar, P. (2018). TPS (think-pair–share): An effective cooperative learning strategy for unleashing discussion in classroom interaction. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 8(5), 91–100.